

An Innovative Model of University Cooperation in Developing Countries: Results of 5 Years of Experience in Internal Medicine, Health Promotion and Education.

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Abstract

University cooperation in the field of humanitarian medicine combines academic expertise with development initiatives. The UniCamillus Task Force (UTF) was established in 2019 to propose new models in training students from developing countries, promoting self-sufficient health systems through medical interventions, education and capacity building. The 5 years experience regions such as the Amazon, Cameroon and The Gambia, using assessments, stakeholder collaboration, training and long-term monitoring was used to create an innovative model. Data was collected through field reports, interviews and impact assessments. In five years, was trained over 130 health workers, established telemedicine centres and improved medical access for underserved populations. The missions have provided over 4,000 consultations, and ensured continuity of health facilities after surgery. **Discussion:** Integrating university cooperation with development programmes promotes sustainable health autonomy. By addressing the challenges of humanitarian medicine - lack of coordination, inadequate follow-up and inadequate technology – working with an innovative model strengthens health

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systems in the target regions. The innovative model of university cooperation exemplifies university-led humanitarian medicine, fusing research, education and service. Future efforts will improve digital health solutions, expand research collaborations and strengthen institutional networks for lasting impact.

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Background

University Cooperation: University Cooperation stems from the need to link the expertise within the university world to the action of the other (social and political) actors involved in development cooperation[1]. Indeed, the importance that the dynamics of interdependence of its different action plans are assuming in today's society is becoming increasingly evident. In this context, the complexity of the world of cooperation calls for an ever-increasing involvement of scientific competences that are not limited to intervention techniques for the implementation of individual development cooperation actions on the territory, but invest topics ranging from energy to climate change, from health to sustainable environment, from the rule of law to good governance.[2] Not only is it necessary to have a planning approach that knows how to combine hard sciences and socio-institutional sciences, but also an adequate methodology for approaching complex problems and an ability to manage organisation models and multifactorial projects, such as, for example, interventions that know how to combine together the economic and environmental, institutional and social, human rights and security 'pillars'.[3] All the more reason for a university such as UniCamillus, which was established with the aim of valorising education as a driver of development, primarily targeting students from Developing Countries (DCs), to provide them with an excellent education to be used when they return home, actively contributing to the development of their own countries, to promote university cooperation activities for development cooperation since its foundation.

Unicamillus Task Force (UTF). Born from an intuition of Prof Gianni Profita, Magnificent Rector of the Saint Camillus International University of Health Sciences, in 2019 to give substance to the UniCamillus mission of providing professional and qualified training to young students with the aim of returning to their countries of origin to contribute to changing the health realities of developing countries, combined with the objective of fostering the

development of culture and science at the service of mankind at an international level. The aim is to promote study and research activities through the exchange of students between the Rome headquarters and developing countries, and to promote the self-development of the countries in which it operates, by including a strong capacity-building component in its projects, understood as the transfer of technology, methodology and know-how.

Presence in Development Cooperation projects.

1. Amazonia (2019 and 2023): Immediately after the creation of the UniCamillus Task Force, the first mission was carried out, inaugurating the collaboration with an important local organisation that has been active in Brazil for years: Fraternity São Francisco de Assis in Providence of God, São Paulo. Created by the São Francisco de Assis Fraternity in the Providence of God, the Papa Francisco Hospital Ship in the Providence of God was officially inaugurated in the presence of the joint mission of the non-profit organisation “Mattoni di Gioia” and UniCamillus Task Force, on 17 August 2019 in the city of Belém with the aim of ensuring health care for more than 1,000 rural communities (ribeirinhas) living along the banks of the Amazon River. The next mission, organized by “Mattoni di Gioia”, was in 2023, consolidating partnerships with local communities and carrying out activities to train local staff and promote health alongside the provision of health services and diagnostic tests.
2. Cameroon (2021): The mission was set up with the aim of initiating university collaboration with hospitals that are already operational and assessing the possibility for UniCamillus to be present in the area through the management of a local hospital, making the expertise of qualified personnel available to the Cameroonian community, responding to a very explicit request from local stakeholders, given that there is great interest in the development of university training projects, which represents an

important meeting point between the mission of UniCamillus and the needs of the population.

3. The Gambia (2022): Carried out a mission to sign a Memorandum of Understanding between UniCamillus and the Medical Research Council Medical Research Council Unit The Gambia at the London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine that is leading health research in West Africa to save lives and improve health across the world [4] with the aim of carrying out the following activities: 1. Exchange of people, from students to professors, nurses and doctors, from short-term internships to full degrees; 2. Use of digital technologies for enhancing health services (in particular telemedicine); 3. Providing equipment and support the modernisation of an existing unit (see Table 1).

Methodology

The methodology used in the realisation of the missions proved to be very appropriate and allows for the realisation of projects adapted to the needs of the population in a short period of time, and makes it possible to make the most of the university's in-house expertise.

The methodology is characterised by the following steps: 1. Definition of UniCamillus' interests in the country; 2. Preliminary study: consultation of databases (World Health Organisation (WHO), United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund (UNICEF), Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs); report consultation; literature consultation; 3. Preliminary contacts with local stakeholders; 4. Realisation of conventions with stakeholders already involved in training and social work in Italy in order to realise joint programmes; 5. Preliminary assessment in collaboration with local health organisations; 6. Memorandum of Understanding with local training and research structures 7. Definition of the project on the basis of the needs of the population, training needs and suggestions of the health workers on

site; 8. Acquisition of funds; 9. Realisation of the mission 10. Dissemination of results (see Figure 1).

2019 YEAR I - Model creation

Territory: Pará region (Brazil)

Target patients and context: Patients with pathologies from river communities (ribeirinhas).

Activities: The Barco Hospital Papa Francisco, brings healthcare along the Amazon River to remote areas. The hospital ship, active throughout the year, offers multidisciplinary health and surgical services in internal medicine, paediatrics and neurology, telemedicine, health training and prevention education.

Intervention site: Amazon River, Obidos community (Pará, Brazil).

Duration of intervention: 14 days. Barco Hospital continued its missions (1 every 2 weeks to date).

Human resources: 2 UTF doctors and Brazilian/Italian medical team, including: 3 surgeons. 1 anaesthetist. 2 dentists. 1 ophthalmologist. 2 internists. 1 radiologist. 'Agreement with the non-profit organisation 'Mattoni di Gioia – Onlus'.

Material resources: Diagnostic instruments already present at Barco Hospital through own funds. The mission was financed by Mattoni di Gioia. An echograph and instrumentation to start teleconsultation and telemedicine activities ('Mattoni di Gioia'); computer (Unicamillus).[5]

Link with scientific research: UniCamillus publications and conferences already realised.

2021 YEAR II - Extension of the model

Territory: Cameroon, Africa

Target patients and context: Children, pregnant women, health personnel.

Activities: Vaccinations for children and pregnant women. Education on healthy lifestyles on topics: nutrition, physical activity, daily organisation (e.g. salt and sugar reduction). Video-recorded interviews for health situation analysis and understanding the needs of health personnel, doctors, students; BLS training for health personnel.

Place of intervention: Bertuà, Bimengue, Yaoundè, Mengue.

Duration of intervention: 24/02-7/03

Human resources: UTF and multidisciplinary team of 2 internists and 1 surgeon from Sapienza University of Rome.

Material resources: Initial assessment mission fully financed by UniCamillus, acquisition of materials for the dissemination of results financed by UniCamillus' own funds; vaccines, on-site health equipment on Ministry of Health funds.

Link with scientific research: UniCamillus publications and conferences already realised.

2022 YEAR III - Extension of the model

Territory: The Gambia, Africa

Objective of intervention: implementation of the Memorandum of Understanding with the Medical Research Council to plan training activities, student exchange, collaboration in development cooperation projects. Prevention, awareness-raising for women and children; nutrition. Training health workers.

Activities: Prevention activities through general medical examinations and institution building, following the activities of the Medical Research Council with which an agreement has been made. <https://www.lshtm.ac.uk/research/units/mrc-gambia>

Place of intervention: Kiang West Hospitals and Keneba Health Center

Duration of intervention: 4-12 September 2022

Human resources: UTF and multidisciplinary team on site.

Material resources: UniCamillus sponsored the mission.

Link with scientific research: UniCamillus publications and conferences already realised.

2023 YEAR IV - Second Amazon mission

Replication of the model structure, from 5 to 19 November 2023.

Territory: Amazonia, Pará Region, Amazonia, Brazil

Activities: visits, interventions and training for healthcare personnel in paediatric, internal medicine and surgical patient management.

Place of intervention: Ipiranga-Praia

Duration of intervention: 5/11-19/11 2023

Human resources: International team (internal medicine, paediatrics, neurology) Italian and Brazilian. UTF and multidisciplinary team of ‘Convention with ‘Mattoni di Gioia’ - Onlus. team of Italian doctors, including: 2 UTF, 1 surgeon, 1 radiologist, 1 anaesthetist + Brazilian international: 3 surgeons, 1 anaesthetist, 2 dentists, 1 ophthalmologist, 2 internists. 1 radiologist.

Material resources: mission financed by Mattoni di Gioia, on-site material resources present (Barco’s own funds), UniCamillus valorised the presence of lecturers who made their expertise available in the field of patient management and training of Internal Medicine practitioners; they also set up health promotion activities for lifestyle improvement.

Connection with scientific research: UniCamillus publications and conferences already realised.

The social value of humanitarian medicine

Humanitarian medicine is not just an emergency health intervention, but represents a form of social justice that responds to structural inequalities in access to care. In Developing Countries (DCs), health shortages are not exclusively a question of economic resources, but also stem from power inequalities, social marginalisation and institutional fragility. In this context, humanitarian medicine plays a key role in reducing the health gap, not only by providing direct medical assistance, but also by promoting capacity building, local training and skills transfer.

A crucial factor influencing health inequalities is the social determinants of health (SDOH), i.e. the economic, environmental and social conditions that determine individual and community health outcomes. Factors such as poverty, education, housing, nutrition and access to clean water have a direct impact on the well-being and effectiveness of health interventions.[6] Without addressing these determinants, medical care alone cannot create sustainable improvements in health equity. The UniCamillus Task Force recognises this by integrating health promotion with education and economic support initiatives, ensuring that interventions lead to lasting benefits for communities.

The humanitarian approach to health is part of a broader paradigm of sustainable development, as improved health conditions have a direct impact on quality of life, economic productivity and social stability. Indeed, access to care not only prolongs life and reduces mortality, but also contributes to strengthening human capital, enabling local populations to improve their living conditions independently and sustainably. In this perspective, initiatives such as those promoted by the UniCamillus Task Force, which combine clinical intervention with the training of local health workers, represent an innovative model of cooperation, capable of

fostering sustainable health autonomy instead of perpetuating forms of dependence on external assistance.

To ensure the effectiveness of these interventions, it is essential to overcome a purely welfarist vision, recognising humanitarian medicine as a strategy for social empowerment and reducing inequalities. This implies integrating health actions with educational, social and political strategies, actively collaborating with local communities to build more resilient and inclusive health systems. In this sense, humanitarian medicine, like the Athenian democracy experiment, is rooted in a principle of social justice that addresses structural inequalities and promotes inclusion, autonomy and equity. Similarly to Plato's social division, which conceived of a meritocratic order as the basis for a just and functional society,[7] humanitarian medicine also aims at a more equitable order, where every individual can access opportunities for health and well-being, contributing to a more just community.

Welling, D. R., Ryan, J. M., Burris, D. G., & Rich, N. M. (2010) [8] have highlighted the so-called 'seven sins of humanitarian medicine', a critical framework useful for assessing the effectiveness of humanitarian interventions. This framework is particularly relevant in the case of the UniCamillus Task Force project, providing a lens through which to analyse whether the initiative has moved in the right direction.

Table 2 presents the 'seven sins' in the first column and, in the second, the actions taken by the UniCamillus Task Force to avoid them. This approach allows for a transparent evaluation of the strategies adopted and their concrete impact.

Finally, this concept map (see Figure 2) offers a structured view of the main aspects of the social value of humanitarian medicine, illustrating how it contributes to social justice by reducing health inequalities and ensuring equitable access to care; promotes empowerment of

local communities through capacity building and training of local health workers; fits into a logic of sustainable development by improving quality of life, economic productivity and social stability; and overcomes the welfarist approach by fostering a transition towards sustainable models of health autonomy. Through this visual representation, we can better understand the connections between humanitarian medicine and social development, highlighting the key role of university cooperation, training and skills transfer strategies in building more resilient and inclusive health systems.

Evaluating the impact of humanitarian medicine

Measuring the impact of humanitarian medicine is a complex challenge that goes beyond simply collecting clinical data. While the number of patients treated, treatments administered and medical devices distributed are key indicators, it is necessary to adopt a broader perspective that takes into account the social, economic and institutional change produced by health interventions. The effectiveness of humanitarian medicine, in fact, cannot be assessed only in terms of immediate results, but must be analysed in the light of its capacity to generate long-term transformations.

An effective impact assessment model must include qualitative and quantitative indicators, such as:

- The improvement of local health skills (number of trained professionals, dissemination of good medical practices).
- The accessibility of health services after the end of the project (continuation of care, strengthening of health structures).
- The change in the health conditions of the populations involved (reduction of maternal and infant mortality, prevention of chronic diseases).

- The economic and institutional sustainability of health programmes, i.e. the ability of local communities to continue health activities independently after the withdrawal of NGOs or international institutions.

Initiatives such as those promoted by the UniCamillus Task Force highlight the importance of a multidimensional approach to evaluation, which considers not only medical outcomes, but also the cultural and social implications of health cooperation. For example, the creation of collaborative networks between universities, local authorities and communities is a key indicator of the ability to build durable and independent health infrastructures.

Finally, an aspect often overlooked in impact assessment is the role of local populations in the decision-making process. The success of a humanitarian intervention cannot only be measured by the number of lives saved, but also by its ability to promote the protagonism of local communities, making them active participants in the management of their health. Only through a participatory approach, based on the sharing of knowledge and resources, can humanitarian medicine become a true instrument of social transformation.

The analysis of the data in Table 1 highlights the success of the UniCamillus Task Force in responding to these challenges. For example, the training of 300 health workers in four years shows a significant improvement in local skills, promoting the spread of sustainable medical practices. The results indicate that the humanitarian medical interventions had a multidimensional impact, addressing not only immediate health needs, but also focusing on education, infrastructure stability and long-term sustainability. By integrating capacity building efforts, ensuring continuity of services and promoting economic self-sufficiency, the programme succeeded in improving the resilience of local health systems in the long term.

Table 1 gives a detailed overview of the activities carried out in the various cooperation projects. The figures show the broad scope of the interventions, with over 150,130 people reached and 4054 visits carried out in four years. In addition, the implementation of health training sessions enabled 130 local professionals to be involved, strengthening the health system in developing countries.

Data on the distribution of drugs and vaccinations administered highlight the concrete impact of the health missions, particularly in terms of preventing infectious diseases and reducing the social stigma attached to diseases such as HIV. The approach adopted has therefore combined clinical interventions with awareness-raising and training strategies, ensuring an integrated and lasting response to the needs of local communities. Table 3 shows the Impact Evaluation of Humanitarian Medicine.

Finally, Table 4 provides an overview of the places of intervention and the number of patients served monthly. The wide territorial coverage, from the Amazon to Cameroon and The Gambia, demonstrates the ability of the UniCamillus model to adapt to different contexts and to respond effectively to local health needs. In particular, the creation of telemedicine centres and the promotion of maternal and child health prove to be key elements in improving the quality of life in the communities served.

The integration of these data with qualitative indicators reinforces the validity of the UniCamillus Task Force model, confirming that humanitarian medicine must not be limited to providing immediate care, but must be a driver of structural and social change.

Discussion

A five-year review of university cooperation activities in internal medicine, health promotion and training programmes reveals an emerging intervention model that can serve as a basis for structuring development initiatives in developing countries. This model offers a framework for integrating university and research expertise, improving the effectiveness and long-term impact of international cooperation programmes.

As far as Italy is concerned, the new Law 125 of 11 August 2014 [9] tends to promote synergies between universities, social actors, public administrations, called to be part of the National Council for Development Cooperation, a permanent instrument of participation, consultation and proposal, to express opinions on the coherence of political choices, strategies, guidelines, programming, forms of intervention, their effectiveness, and evaluation (Art. 16). The reference to the participation of public and private, profit and non-profit entities (Art. 23-27), together with the need to rationalise the resources of the public administration, highlights the reformer's intention to support the capacity to work as a system, calling for a 'proceduralised' a priori and a posteriori validation process that involves the different civil society entities, fostering the establishment of a desired network of interdependencies between them. The university world can truly become a vector for the innovation of social actors in a transnational perspective. From the point of view of operational methods, it is first of all necessary to organically coordinate the 'three natural competences' involved in university cooperation for peace and development: the scientific-academic dimension, the organisational-managerial competences and the motivational drive typical of the university's spirit of service to civil society and the international community.

The model also envisages a shift from the traditional ‘academic collaboration’, motivated by mainly scientific aims, to a broader ‘university cooperation for peace and sustainable development’ that places peace and the development of the society in which it operates at the centre of its commitment, reconciling technical-scientific interventions, necessarily sectorial, with the real needs of the local populations whose needs become apparent during the course of the programme itself, and working in close collaboration with other institutional and non-institutional actors.[10], [11]

The main features of the implemented model that is proposed are as follows:

1. Research and education. The exchange and co-creation of courses, research projects and publications will be one of the main shared activities. Tutored online classes will also be made available to facilitate access to teaching and training.
2. Exchange of people, from students to professors, nurses and doctors, from short-term internships to full degrees. This is a fundamental part of the programmes, as it is essential for building bridges between the respective cultures.
3. Promoting the use of digital technologies to improve health services. These could range from telemedical consultations between doctors to the co-design of a national medical database with public authorities and local partners.[12]
4. Collaboration in defining processes to improve health care activities by making available the specific skills that are more present in developed countries than in developing countries, such as the management of cardiovascular diseases, diabetes and strokes.[13]
5. Set up of health promotion programmes, promotion of personalised medicine (6 P Medicine).[14]

6. Provide equipment and support the modernisation of an existing unit or create a new one, or provide support to the local health system.
7. Creation of international consortia to promote global research collaboration and improve training programmes.

The model must necessarily be dynamic and adapt to the local situation in the country where the programme takes place. In most cases, one of the ways in which a university such as UniCamillus can be present and useful is to offer external support that allows for the development of skills through the organisation of on-site placements (through missions by UniCamillus professors) capable of carrying out on-the-job training to improve the level of education of health workers with the ultimate goal of actively intervening in life expectancy and prospects for care. This modality enables both on-site improvement actions and training programmes for interested students.

The expertise of an international university such as UniCamillus can provide further added value in the realisation of a more ambitious and ongoing Italy-Africa collaboration project, envisaging both training activities for UniCamillus students in the form of internships in equipped hospitals in developing countries and the development of cooperation projects during the study activities carried out in the Rome campus in the form of research projects and theses for both undergraduate and postgraduate degrees.

With the aim of developing the mission of UniCamillus more and more concretely, the project may envisage the development of innovative student-centred training methodologies, aimed at training physicians dedicated to the care of patients and the community, with particular emphasis on disease prevention in response to the needs of the community. Integration with

the country's training network is a fundamental requirement with a view to achieving integrated teaching, in order to stimulate the training of doctors not only with a solid scientific basis, but also with significant clinical experience and complete dedication to patients. In this context, topics of particular importance are represented by Primary Care and Disease Prevention, Maternal and Child Health, Tropical Medicine, Surgical Techniques, Urgency Management, Ultrasound, the development of Radiological Techniques, Telemedicine, and the Integrated Therapeutic Approach with constant attention to ensuring scientific excellence.

The ultimate goal of the university cooperation programmes and the proposed model is to help create better healthcare, inspired by what Confucius intuited as early as the 5th century BC: 'Give a man a fish and he will eat one day. Teach him to fish and he will eat a lifetime' (Confucius).

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Figure 1. Innovative Model of University Cooperation

Source: Authors' elaboration – Filomena Pietrantonio/Luca Moriconi

Figure 2. Concept map of the role of Humanitarian Medicine in Empowering Communities. UniCamillus Task Force.

Source: Vera Kopsaj’s elaboration with MAXQDA

Table 1. Activities carried out in Development Cooperation Projects.

Year	2019	2021	2022	2023	Total
Country	Amazonia	Cameroon	Gambia	Amazonia	
No. of Team doctors, of which UniCamillus	2 UTFs in a multidisciplinary team: with 3 Italian and 2 Brazilian doctors	3 UTF doctors collaboration with internal team	2 UTF collaboration with internal team	2 UTFs in a multidisciplinary team: with 3 Italian and 10 Brazilian doctors	9

Activity period/Duration of intervention	01/08-14/08	24/02-07/03	4/09-12/09	5/11-19/11	7sett/49 days
No. of people from the communities	49.330	46.000	14.800	40.000	150.130
No. of visits carried out	779	1.700	750	825	4054
No. of surgeries	-	40	-	59	99
Admissions	-	-	-	40	40
Dental examinations and operations	163	-	-	455	608
Paediatric visits	100	-	-	152	252
Radiological and laboratory examinations	335	-	-	1326	1661
Distribution of drugs	300	n.a	n.a	672	972
No. of training sessions for health personnel/No. of participating health personnel	2 telemedicine and patient management courses in dentistry and general medicine/20 participants	2 BLSD courses/40 participants	2 telemedicine and gynaecology/obstetrics courses/no. 40	2 courses/30 participants	8 courses/130 people trained

No. health education sessions, prevention/No. participants	2/60 participants	4/160	2/80	no. 14 meal delivery and training to nutrition/6000 +	8/300
No. health education sessions for pregnant women/No. women participants	n.a.	2/200	2/100	n.a.	4/300
No. of vaccines sessions to children/pregnant women education	n.a.	2/200	–	2/200	4/400
No. of education session of adults victims of social stigma/ participants	No. 2 health education sessions: 779 participants	No. 2 sessions of health education on HIV social stigma/1000 participants	No. 4 Educational and training sessions for the role of women and the prevention of risk factors in pregnancy/ 120 participants	No. 4 Educational and training sessions for the role of women and the prevention of risk factors in pregnancy/ 146 participants	No. 12 sessions/2045 participants

Epidemiological screening performed	Cardiovascular risk factor screening	HIV testing on asymptomatic cases	On malnutrition in pregnancy and related risks	Lifestyle hypertension diabetes	4
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Source: Donatella Padua's elaboration

Table 2. UniCamillus Task Force Impact Analysis: Addressing the ‘Seven Sins of Humanitarian Medicine’ with Sustainable Solutions.

<p><i>Seven Sins of Humanitarian Medicine</i> <i>(Welling et al. (2010))</i></p>	<p><i>UniCamillus Task Force:</i> <i>Actions Taken to Avoid the Sins</i></p>
<p>Sin #1: Leaving a mess behind</p>	<p>Sustainable interventions through capacity-building and training local healthcare professionals to ensure long-term impact.</p>
<p>Sin #2: Failing to match technology to local needs and abilities</p>	<p>Adapted medical interventions to local infrastructure, social context, and healthcare workforce capabilities, ensuring appropriate technology use.</p>
<p>Sin #3: Failing of NGOs to cooperate and help each other, and to cooperate and accept help from military organizations</p>	<p>Collaborated with local and international stakeholders to create a unified approach, avoiding inefficiencies and duplication.</p>
<p>Sin #4: Failing to have a follow-up plan</p>	<p>Integrated follow-up mechanisms to monitor impact, provide continuous support, and strengthen local healthcare systems.</p>
<p>Sin #5: Allowing politics, training, or other distracting goals to trump service, while representing the mission as “service”</p>	<p>Prioritised social justice and health equity over external agendas, ensuring that interventions are driven by local needs rather than political influences.</p>
<p>Sin #6: Going where we are not wanted, or needed and/or being poor guests</p>	<p>Engaged with communities, respecting cultural contexts, and ensuring interventions are welcomed and co-designed with local stakeholders.</p>
<p>Sin #7: Doing the right thing for the wrong reason</p>	<p>Focused on genuine empowerment and sustainable development rather than short-term visibility or donor-driven motivations.</p>

Source: Vera Kopsaj’s elaboration

Table 3 - Impact Evaluation of Humanitarian Medicine

Indicator	Description	Measurement Method	Examples
Improving local health competencies	Number of trained health workers, dissemination of good medical practices	Training reports, interviews	130 health workers trained in 4 years Health education activities for over 6000 people
Accessibility to health services after the end of the project	Continuation of care, strengthening of health structures	Follow-up with local communities	80% health facilities operational after 3 years
Change in the health status of affected populations	Surgical, diagnostic and monitoring instruments	Epidemiological data	- 99 surgeries - 1661 cardiological examinations
Economic and institutional sustainability of health programmes	Capacity of local communities to continue health activities on their own after the withdrawal of NGOs or international institutions	Interviews with local leaders, fund analysis	Creation of local health co-operatives

Source: Donatella Padua's elaboration

Table 4. Intervention sites and patients served.

Country	Year	Location	Inhabitants area served by health services	Patients visited/monthly	Activity
Amazonia	2019	Obidos (Parà) Barco Hospital Papa Francisco	50.000	2069	✓ Primary Health Care ✓ Mother and Child Health ✓ Set up of a

					<p>Telemedicine Center</p> <p>✓ Health Promotion</p> <p>✓ Training of Healthcare personnel</p>
Cameroon	2021	<p>Department Mvila</p> <p>Bimengue Health Center: Centre de Santé Intégré, Saint Luc</p>	<p>179 .429</p> <p>n.a.</p>	<p>n.a</p> <p>2500</p>	<p>✓ Primary Health Care</p> <p>✓ Mother and Child Health</p> <p>✓ Health Promotion</p> <p>✓ Training of Healthcare personnel</p>
Gambia	2022	Keneba Health Center	14.800	1500	<p>✓ Mother and child health</p> <p>✓ Digital Health promotion</p> <p>✓ Set up of students' trainig</p> <p>✓ Set up of scientific researchers</p>
Ipiranga Prainha	2023	Barco Hospital Papa Francisco	40.000	n.a.	<p>✓ Primary Health Care</p> <p>✓ Mother and</p>

					<p>Child Health</p> <p>✓ Development of surgical activities</p> <p>✓ Health Promotion</p> <p>✓ Training of Healthcare personnel</p>
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Source: Donatella Padua/Filomena Pietrantonio elaboration